

Formation of Intermetallic Compound in Composite Materials

K. Motoki, A. Okura

Institute of Industrial Science, University of Tokyo, 22-1, Roppongi 7-chome, Minato-ku, Tokyo 106, Japan

ABSTRACT

This paper describes about the formation of aluminum carbide at the interface between aluminum and carbon. By anneal for an hour double film of aluminum and carbon reacts to form aluminum carbide at 350°C or above. And by existence of aluminum oxide at the interface lower limit of reaction temperature rises. Carbon fiber (HT type) and aluminum react by anneal for four hours at 550°C or above, for an hour at 620°C or above. For quantification of reaction between aluminum and carbon fiber, weight reduction of carbon fiber before and after the anneal is measured, which is proportional to the formed quantity of aluminum carbide. Thus the relation between formed quantity of aluminum carbide, tensile strength and surface of carbon fibers is discussed below.

INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber which has high modulus and strength is one of the most attractive fibers, and carbon fiber reinforced aluminum composite is very promising because of its light weight. But, kept at high temperature degradation of tensile strength of Al-C.F. composite occurs and this is attributed to the formation of aluminum carbide at the interface between aluminum and carbon (1^{v4}). Reactivity of aluminum and carbon is studied first by J.J. Trillat et al.(5) The purpose of this report is to identify the product clearly and to clarify the relation between reacted quantity and tensile strength.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Observation and Analysis of Al-C Double Film

In the first place, interfacial reaction between aluminum and carbon was examined by using double films of aluminum and carbon, which was analogous to J. J. Trillat et al. (5) as was convenient for analysis. Double films of carbon and aluminum were prepared by vacuum evaporation described as follows. Carbon was evaporated onto (100) surface of NaCl single crystal and aluminum onto them in vacuum less than 5×10^{-5} Torr (Specimen A), on the other hand, first aluminum and then carbon were evaporated onto (100) surface of NaCl crystal (Specimen B). After NaCl crystal was dissolved in water, double films of carbon and aluminum were mounted on Mo mesh for transmission electron microscope (TEM). These specimens were annealed for an hour at various temperature (300°C, 350°C, 400°C,

450°C, 500°C, 550°C, 600°C, 640°C). And they were observed by TEM (JEM-1250).

Observation and Analysis of Aluminum Evaporated Carbon Fibers

As approach to the actual system, reactivity of aluminum and carbon fiber was examined. Carbon fiber (HT type) was coated with aluminum (99.999%) by vacuum evaporation (10^{-5} Torr) with thickness about 5000 Å. These fibers were annealed for one and four hours at temperature 450°C, 500°C, 550°C, 620°C, in vacuum less than 5×10^{-5} Torr. After annealed, these fibers were observed by TEM (JEM-1250).

Measurement of Weight Reduction and Tensile Test of Carbon Fibers

Further, for quantification of this reaction the following experiment is carried out. A bundle of 12000 carbon fibers (HT type,) were spread and aluminum (99.999%) was evaporated onto them at pressure less than 3×10^{-5} Torr. Two parts of just 3cm long were cut from this bundle. One is annealed at 600°C for 9 hours in vacuum (5×10^{-5} Torr) and the other is without anneal then coating of the fibers were dissolved by hot HCl solution and hot HNO₃ solution. Annealing is carried out also at 630°C for 16 hours using another specimens. After the coating was dissolved only carbon fibers remain and the weight difference between annealed carbon fibers and carbon fibers without anneal were measured. This difference of weight corresponds to the quantity of carbon which contribute to the reaction. The same experiment is carried out with ion plated carbon fiber sheet which is commercially manufactured. Carbon fibers which compose the ion plated sheet are HT type with matrix Al 5056 alloy whose thickness is about 7µm. These carbon fibers were tensile tested at R.T. with gauge length 1.5 cm at a strain rate of 0.4 mm/min, and observed by scanning electron microscope (SEM).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Observation and Analysis of Al-C Double Film

Aluminum film of specimen A is almost polycrystal on the carbon, but that of specimen B has [111] preferred orientation normal to the film. Electron diffraction pattern from specimen A is shown in Fig.1. Only diffraction pattern from aluminum is recognized and that from carbon can not seen because carbon film is amorphous. Diffraction patterns, as shown in Fig.2, were obtained from specimen A annealed at 600°C. This pattern shows the existence of aluminum and aluminum carbide (Al₄C₃) formed at the interface of aluminum and carbon. Aluminum carbide is polycrystal and {012}, {110} reflection beam are strong but {107} reflection beam is weak. And the same result was obtained with specimen B. Fig.2 (d) shows the {110} dark field image, which shows that aluminum carbide grows with small crystal grains. Annealed at 640°C diffraction patterns from γ-Al₂O₃ and Al and Al₄C₃ were observed. Electron diffraction pattern from other specimens annealed at various temperature shows that specimens A reacted at 350°C or above and specimen B reacted at 500°C or above. Below these temperature no reaction is observed. The difference of lower limit of reaction temperature between specimen A and specimen B is considered to be caused because of the existence of aluminum oxide at the interface between aluminum and carbon of specimen B. This aluminum oxide was formed by oxygen in residual gas on aluminum film in vacuum at the interval between aluminum evaporation and carbon evaporation, which is about 10 minutes. And it is considered that the oxide film acted as diffusion barrier to prevent reaction.

Observation and Analysis of Aluminum Evaporated Carbon Fibers

After carbon fibers were annealed for four hours at 620°C they were cut by a blade and electron diffraction pattern (Fig.3 (a)) was obtained from the location of the cut edge. Fig.3 (b) is the photograph of carbon fiber with Al, where diffraction pattern was obtained. This diffraction pattern, which correctly agrees with that of annealed double film of aluminum and carbon (Fig.3 (c)), indicate the existence of aluminum carbide. And diffraction pattern of carbon fiber was also observed with that of aluminum carbide. Aluminum carbide is also identified in the specimen annealed at 550°C for four hours and not identified at below 550°C. Annealed for an hour, at 620°C aluminum carbide can be detected but can not at 550°C or below. Thus carbide formation at interface

between aluminum and carbon fiber is confirmed, and this reaction is less reactive than double film of aluminum and carbon.

Measurement of Weight Reduction and Tensile Test of Carbon Fibers

Weight reduction percentage and ultimate tensile strength of carbon fibers obtained in this experiment are shown in Table 1. Weight reduction percentage is calculated by $w-w_0/w_0 \times 100(\%)$ where w_0 is the weight before anneal and w is after anneal. It is seen that the weight of carbon fibers decrease after annealing by a few percent or below. As aluminum carbide is reactive with water and dilute acid, this decrease shows the amount of carbon which were used for the formation of aluminum carbide. Weight reduction of carbon fiber annealed for 16 hours at 630°C is more than that annealed for 9 hours at 600°C, that is, more reaction occurs when annealed for 16 hours at 630°C than for 9 hours 600°C. Weight increase is recognized in the case of carbon fiber with coatings Al 5056 annealed for 9 hours at 600°C, which is due to errors in measurement.

Original carbon fibers coated by aluminum evaporation has higher ultimate tensile strength than that coated by ion-plating. In each kind of carbon fibers ultimate tensile strength decreases with reducing weight of carbon fibers after anneal. And as shown in Table 1, almost no decrease of ultimate tensile strength was observed with carbon fibers with no coatings annealed for 16 hours at 630°C in vacuum. These results show that decrease of ultimate tensile strength of annealed carbon fibers is because of the surface damage given to carbon fiber by reaction between aluminum and carbon.

Ultimate tensile strength of pure aluminum evaporated carbon fibers after annealed for 9 hours at 600°C is 61% of that of original carbon fibers before anneal and 29% for annealed for 16 hours at 630°C. Ultimate tensile strength of 5056 Al ion-plated carbon fibers after anneal is 66% and 51% respectively. As described above, decrease of ultimate tensile strength of 5056 Al ion-plated carbon fibers is less than that of pure aluminum evaporated carbon fibers. This is considered to be the effect of added elements such as Mg, Si, Fe et al. About this detailed study is in progress.

If weight reduction of carbon fiber was used for homogeneous formation of Al_4C_3 on the surface of carbon fiber, radius of fiber decreases by 110 Å at 0.6% weight reduction, 140 Å at 0.8%, 350 Å at 2%. But it is unreliable that this slight decrease of fiber radius cause considerable decrease of ultimate tensile strength. In Fig.4 SEM observation of carbon fiber after coatings were dissolved is shown and indicates that surface condition of carbon fiber changes to rough. This shows inhomogeneous reaction of aluminum and carbon fiber, therefore, it is considered that stress concentration occurs at some region of rough surface and ultimate tensile strength decreases. And the more weight of carbon fiber reduce by reaction, the rougher the surface of fiber becomes, the more ultimate tensile strength decrease.

CONCLUSION

- (1) Double film of aluminum and carbon reacts to form aluminum carbide annealed for an hour at 350°C or above.
- (2) Carbon fibers and evaporated aluminum react to form aluminum carbide annealed for four hours at 550°C or above and for an hour at 620°C or above.
- (3) Weight of carbon fiber reduces after coating is dissolved because of reaction with aluminum. Weight of carbon fiber with aluminum coating reduces more after anneal than that of carbon fiber with Al 5056 alloy, and, therefore, ultimate tensile strength decrease more than with Al 5056 alloy. This seems to be the effect of added elements.
- (4) The more the weight of carbon fiber reduce, the rougher the surface of carbon fiber becomes. And it is considered that rough surface causes stress concentration, therefore carbon fiber breaks easily.

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Table 1 Effect of anneal on weight reduction and ultimate tensile strength of carbon fiber

Coating	Annealing Temp. (°C)	Annealing Time (hr)	Weight Reduction (%)	UTS (kg/mm ²)
non	630	16	-	372
Al	No anneal	-	-	400
Al	600	9	- 0.8	244
Al	630	16	- 2.0	116
Al 5056	No anneal	-	-	307
Al 5056	600	9	+ 0.6	203
Al 5056	630	16	- 0.6	156

Al : by vacuum evaporation

Al 5056 : by ion plating

Fig. 1 Carbon-aluminum film before anneal: (a) Bright field image
(b) Diffraction pattern

Fig. 2 Carbon-aluminum film annealed for 1 hr at 600°C: (a) Diffraction pattern
(b) Indexing, (c) Bright field image, (d) $\{110\}$ dark field image.

Fig. 3 Examination of carbon fiber coated with aluminum annealed for 4 hr at 600°C: (a) Diffraction pattern, (b) Bright field image of location where (a) is obtained, (c) Comparison of diffraction pattern of (a) (left-half) with that from carbon-aluminum film annealed for 1hr at 600°C (right-half).

(a)

(b)

(c)

5 μm

Fig. 4 Scanning electron micrograph of carbon fiber of which coating was dissolved after anneal: (a) Without anneal, (b) Annealed for 9hr at 600°C, (c) Annealed for 16hr at 630°C.

